

Rochester Regional Physician Assistant Association Continuing Medical Education Conference Abstracts Collection

Intersections in Medicine: Acute Crises and Chronic Care

Doubletree by Hilton Rochester
1111 Jefferson Rd Rochester, NY 14623
17 April, 2026
Rochester Regional Physician Assistant Association

Editor(s)/Compiler(s): Vincent E. DeRienzo, PA-C, CCAPP, FCCP

--- TABLE OF CONTENTS ---

1. RETREAT IN A BOX – Kathleen McNamara, PA-C, MS
 2. POCUS EXPEDITES CARE FOR POST-PARACENTESIS BLEEDING – Jesse Shuff, PA-C
 3. CRYPTOGENIC ORGANIZING PNEUMONIA: A CASE REPORT – Simone Gibeau, PA-C
 4. SEVERE ANEMIA PRESENTING WITH SHOCK PHYSIOLOGY: A CASE REPORT – Brianna Arre, PA-C
 5. SYSTOLIC BLOOD PRESSURE MANAGEMENT FOLLOWING ENDOVASCULAR THROMBECTOMY IN ACUTE STROKE: A CASE STUDY – Olivia DiMillo, PA-C
-

--- ABSTRACTS ---

RETREAT IN A BOX

Author(s): Kathleen McNamara, PA-C, MS
Affiliations(s): University of Rochester Medical Center
Corresponding Author E-mail: mcnamarakat@gmail.com

Abstract:

Overview: URMCC APP WBI 2024 highlighted need to fit wellness practices into daily clinical life. Retreats are difficult to plan but help create a culture of mindfulness and empathetic team connection to decrease burnout. Wellness leaders recommend shift in focus to optimize occupational wellbeing using a systems approach.

Objective: Using pre-assessment to offer individually curated retreats from a menu of resources will improve accessibility and effectiveness of wellbeing-themed retreats

Method: Provide specific resources and tools for wellness leaders to deliver in department retreats. 10 Wellness Retreat Consultations with 10 different APP departments Qualitative and quantitative analysis of wellbeing outcomes and effectiveness data following retreat completion. Consultation workflow, themes offered, discussion of URMC resources

Key Findings: Making retreat resources more accessible and individualized improved knowledge of wellbeing tools and confidence in planning to enhance occupational wellbeing. Retreats improve wellbeing by fostering connection, reducing stress, and promoting a culture of support. Retreats strengthen team cohesion and communication with shared experiences. Retreats provide space for reflection and renewal in high stress environments. Self awareness exercises and mindfulness practices help combat burnout. Retreats reaffirm purpose and provide validation to reconnect mission with values. Skill building such as resilience training and conflict resolution help teams.

Keywords: Wellness, advanced practice providers, workforce

POCUS EXPEDITES CARE FOR POST-PARACENTESIS BLEEDING

Author(s): Jesse Shuff, PA-C

Affiliations(s): University of Rochester Medical Center

Corresponding Author E-mail: jesse_shuff@urmc.rochester.edu

Abstract:

Introduction: Paracentesis is a common bedside procedure for therapeutic relief of ascites and diagnostic evaluation of its etiology. Although generally safe, with complication rates reported between 0.2%–3.0%, adverse events still occur. This case illustrates how point-of-care ultrasound (POCUS) can rapidly identify a significant post-procedural complication.

Case Description: A 59-year-old woman with cirrhosis and recurrent tense ascites required frequent paracenteses during a prolonged hospitalization. A bedside procedure service was consulted to perform paracentesis. POCUS demonstrated large-volume ascites, with the largest accessible pocket in the left lower quadrant. A vascular survey with ultrasound revealed no vessels along the anticipated needle path. After peritoneal access, the aspirated fluid appeared bloody, differing from her baseline. Post-procedure POCUS showed pulsatile intraperitoneal flow and echogenic swirling fluid consistent with blood mixing with residual ascites, concerning for active arterial hemorrhage. Based on these findings, platelets and cryoprecipitate were administered, and Interventional Radiology (IR) was urgently consulted. After reviewing the bedside ultrasound, IR proceeded directly to intervention without additional imaging or serial laboratory studies. Within one hour of identifying the complication, a third-order lateral branch of the left inferior epigastric artery was successfully embolized.

Discussion: Bloody ascites can be diagnostically challenging, and distinguishing new bleeding from chronic hemoperitoneum often requires serial vitals, laboratory evaluation, or CT angiography. This case demonstrates how POCUS can confirm suspected procedural bleeding in real time and expedite definitive management.

Keywords: Paracentesis; point-of-care ultrasound; POCUS; procedural complication; arterial hemorrhage; interventional radiology; internal medicine

CRYPTOGENIC ORGANIZING PNEUMONIA: A CASE REPORT

Author(s): Simone Gibeau, PA-C

Affiliations(s): University of Rochester Medical Center

Corresponding Author E-mail: simone_gibeau@urmc.rochester.edu

Abstract:

Cryptogenic organizing pneumonia (COP) is a rare (0.001%) interstitial lung disease caused by alveolar epithelial injury, leakage of plasma protein into the alveoli, recruitment of fibroblasts, and formation of fibrin in the airway. It is characterized by granulation tissue within distal airways, often presenting with nonspecific respiratory symptoms and radiographic findings that mimic infectious pneumonia. Though it can present more severe as acute respiratory failure. This diagnosis accounts for 0.001% of interstitial lung diseases in the US as of this year. I report a case of an elderly patient presenting with 2 months of progressive dyspnea unresponsive to a 7 day course of antibiotic therapy requiring high flow nasal cannula for oxygenation support. Chest imaging demonstrated bilateral patchy consolidations with peripheral distribution. Extensive infectious, autoimmune, and malignant workups were negative. Histopathologic evaluation was denied given clinical improvement. After exclusion of secondary causes, a diagnosis of COP was established. The patient was treated with high dose systemic corticosteroids, resulting in rapid clinical and radiologic improvement. This case highlights the importance of considering COP in patients with persistent pneumonia-like illness with no underlying pulmonary pathology, unresponsive to antibiotics. Early recognition is essential, as most studies suggest prompt response to treatment.

Keywords: Cryptogenic organizing pneumonia, respiratory failure, rare diseases

SEVERE ANEMIA PRESENTING WITH SHOCK PHYSIOLOGY: A CASE REPORT

Author(s): Brianna Arre, PA-C

Affiliations(s): University of Rochester Medical Center

Corresponding Author E-mail: brianna_arre1@urmc.rochester.edu

Abstract:

Severe anemia can present with signs of systemic hypoperfusion that mimic hemorrhagic shock, creating diagnostic uncertainty and requiring rapid initial stabilization while maintaining a broad differential diagnosis and workup. This is the case of an 80-year-old male with a history of abdominal aortic and peripheral aneurysms who presented with three days of progressive weakness and malaise. On arrival, laboratory studies revealed profound anemia with hemoglobin <3 g/dL, elevated lactate, evidence of acute kidney injury, and hypotension, raising concern for hemorrhagic shock. Given his vascular history, emergent imaging was performed to evaluate for active bleeding or aneurysmal rupture. CTA of the head, chest, abdomen, and pelvis demonstrated no acute hemorrhage. The patient was initially stabilized with transfusion of packed red blood cells and plasma while further

diagnostic evaluation was pursued. Additional laboratory testing revealed normocytic anemia with a low reticulocyte response and a positive direct antiglobulin test, suggesting an underlying immune-mediated process rather than acute blood loss. This case highlights the importance of reassessing the differential diagnosis in patients presenting with profound anemia and signs of shock physiology. Early resuscitation must occur in parallel with diagnostic evaluation to identify non-hemorrhagic etiologies. Recognition of severe anemia as a potential cause of tissue hypoxia and shock physiology is critical to guide appropriate management and prevent complications such as multiorgan failure.

Keywords: Anemia, critical care, rare presentation

SYSTOLIC BLOOD PRESSURE MANAGEMENT FOLLOWING ENDOVASCULAR THROMBECTOMY IN ACUTE STROKE: A CASE STUDY

Author(s): Olivia DiMillo, PA-C

Affiliations(s): University of Rochester Medical Center

Corresponding Author E-mail: olivia_dimillo1@urmc.rochester.edu

Abstract:

Topic: SBP goals s/p endovascular thrombectomy Case: 91 yo male presenting with right MCA syndrome. Diagnostics including brain imaging, stroke workup, and follow up MRI to assess for hemorrhagic transformation. Interventions: endovascular thrombectomy, statin, SBP goal <180, prn anti-hypertensives Discussion: literature review of Enchanted2/MT trial, BEST-II Trial, and Optimal-BP trial paired with AHA/ACC guidelines Conclusions: aggressive blood pressure management may cause harm in this patient population, despite risk of bleed at less aggressive goals

Keywords: Acute cerebral vascular accident, endovascular thrombectomy, neuromedicine intensive care